

Synthesis and Characterization of Silver Aluminium Selenide (AgAlSe₂), Absorbent Materials prepared by Electrodeposition Technique.

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ABSTRACT,

Silver Aluminium selenide (AgAlSe₂) thin films have been successfully grown through the reaction of AgNO₃, AlCl₃.6H₂O and Selenium metal powder onto glass substrates using electrochemical deposition technique and annealed at 150°C. The resulting thin films were characterized using Rutherford Backscattering Spectroscopy (RBS), UV-VIS Spectrophotometers and X-ray diffractometer to determine the films composition, the optical and structural properties and then to determine the possible areas of application of the films through the analysis of the results of the characterization. Optical analysis of the films revealed high absorbance in the UV region which decreased in the visible and infrared regions as the concentration of selenide ion increases and increased when annealed. The structural analysis indicates that AgAlSe₂ films are of tetragonal crystal structure with lattice constant $a = 5.956 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 5.956 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 10.750 \text{ \AA}$ respectively. The result of the RBS showed that the grown films are rich in silver. The band gap of the deposited films was found to decrease from the range of 3.7eV to 3.95 eV to the range of 3.3 eV to 3.8 eV respectively as a result of annealing at varying concentration of selenide ion. The optical and structural analyses of the films revealed significant effect of annealing and varying concentration of selenide ion on the properties of AgAlSe₂ films. The thin films that exhibit these properties are desirable for photovoltaic devices, optical and opto-electronic applications.

Keywords: Thin Films, electrochemical deposition, AgAlSe₂, absorbance, band gap energy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Thin film technology plays an important role in almost electronic and optical devices. Many industries throughout the world are involved with thin films. It has been applied as electroplated films for decoration and protection (Heaven, 1970). Thin films have long been used as anti-reflection coatings on window glass, video screens, camera lenses and other optical devices. Thin films can be defined as thin materials that form by process of atom-by-atom, molecule-by-molecule, ion-by-ion or cluster of species-by-cluster of species condensation process. Also, a thin film is a very thin layer of a substance on a supporting material; especially: a coating (as of a semiconductor) that is deposited in a layer one atom or one molecule thick. It is layer of material ranging from fractions of a nanometre (monolayer) to several micrometers in thickness. Electronic semi-conductor devices and optical coating are the main applications benefiting from thin film deposition. These films are less than

100nm thick and are made from dielectric transparent materials. They have refractive index less than that of the substrate (Pentia *et al.*, 2004). Thin films have found many applications in today's energy research and other industrial applications.

Renewable energy sources that can be developed include continuous natural energy flows such as sunlight (solar energy), ocean currents, wave, falling water, wind energy whose replenishment is far greater than projected human use. Out of these energy choices, solar energy is certainly one of the most attractive. Since sunlight is mostly abundant in most countries of the world especially the less developed countries mostly Africa; it is hoped that if this particular source of energy is researched into and developed, the bridging of the technological gap between the third world countries and most of the developed countries is then feasible (Nnabuchi, 2004).

Aluminium selenide (Al_2Se_3) has been used as a precursor to produce hydrogen selenide, which is released when the solid is treated with acids. It should be stored away from moisture and air as it is hydrolytically unstable. Heterostructures combining III-VI semiconductors with silicon have attracted attention (Brinker *et al.*, 1991) due to their close lattice matching and promising optoelectronic properties. Al_2Se_3 is the least studied of the group III-VI chalcogenide (Chopra and Das, 1983) when compared to other members of the III-VI family of semiconductors. The first growth of aluminum selenide on silicon is reported by Cui *et al.*, (2003).

Silver selenide, a group I-VI semiconductor compound is a mixed ionic conductor (Kumar and Pradeep 2002). Ag_2Se undergoes a polymorphic phase transition, a low- temperature orthorhombic phase (β - Ag_2Se) at 0 K, and a high temperature cubic phase (α - Ag_2Se) with a transition temperature of 135 °C (Santhosh and Pradeep, 2002; Abdullaev, *et al.*, 2014). Silver selenide exhibits many interesting and useful properties (Sreenivas *et al.*, 1997). A low temperature phase (β - Ag_2Se) is a narrow band gap and n-type semiconductor (Rao *et al.*, 2002) with resistivity of 10^{-3} and 10^{-4} Ωcm (Shukla *et al.*, 1981). β - Ag_2Se is used as a photo-sensitizer in photographic films and in thermochromic materials due to its relatively high Seeback coefficient, low lattice thermal conductivity, and high electrical conductivity (Cui *et al.*, 2003). A high temperature phase (α - Ag_2Se) is a superionic conductor. It finds application in solid electrolytes in photochargeable secondary batteries (Kobayashi, 1990).

Besides, the present research describes synthesis of Silver Aluminium Selenide (AgAlSe_2) thin films by electrochemical technique, using selenium dioxide (powder) as source of Se^{2-} ion and Silver chloride as source Ag^+ and Al_3S as source Al^{3+} ion. The AgAlSe_2 (Ternary) compound belong to group I-III-VI semiconductor thin film. The preparative parameters such as molar concentration of precursor of selenide is to be studied and reported.

2. EXPERIMENTAL DETAIL

The AgAlSe_2 , (AAS) thin films were deposited by by Electrodeposition Technique on glass substrates. A good effort was made to synthesize silver Aluminumselenide from selenium (Se) metal powder, aluminum chloride (AlCl_3) and silver trioxonitrate (v) (AgNO_3) employing electrochemical deposition method. Many trial attempts were made to synthesize AgAlSe_2 from different ratios of the above named materials and finally the following ratio were selected to obtain AgAlSe_2 by electrodeposition techniques:

1. 0.1M $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Aluminum chloride hexahydrate)
2. 0.1M AgNO_3 (Silver trioxonitrate (v)) and
3. 0.1M selenium metal powder (of various molar concentration for variation of selenide source).

Saturated calomel electrode (SCE) and carbon electrode were used as reference electrode and counter electrode respectively. Glass substrates were chosen to be the working electrodes. They were degreased and cleaned with acetone and methanol and allowed to dry in air before electrodeposition.

Substrate Pre-Treatment

In the electrodeposition technique, usually there is need to subject the substrates to distinct pre-treatment to ensure that the presence of catalytic surface is removed to improve the adhesion of the films to the substrates particularly as film thickness increases. This pre-treatment of glass slides substrates involves the following steps;

- i. Cleaning the glass slides with detergents.
- ii. Soaking the slides in acetone for about 15 minutes for degreasing.
- iii. Ultrasonicing the substrates/slides for about 10 minutes in an ultrasonic bath.
- iv. Drying the substrates in an electronic thermal heated dryer called an oven for about 5-10 minutes at a temperature of about 50°C to 60°C .

Figure 3.1: Schematic Diagram of the Electrodeposition Experimental Set up

Preparation of Precursors

0.1 M of AgNO_3 solution was prepared by dissolving 1.7 g of AgNO_3 salt in 100 ml of distilled water. 0.1 M of $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solution was prepared by dissolving 2.41 g of the salt ($\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) in 100 ml of distilled water. These two solutions prepared (ie AgNO_3 and $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solutions) served as the cationic precursor for precipitation of Al^{3+} and Ag^+ ions. Also, 0.1 M selenium solution was prepared by dissolving 0.79 g of selenium metal powder in 100 ml of distilled water.

Variation of molar concentration of selenide ion

AAS (AgAlSe_2) films were deposited at room temperature at a constant voltage of 10 Volts for 5 minutes at a five variable/different molar concentration of selenide source as seen in

table one below. The three chemicals prepared were kept in three different beakers. 12 ml of each of the chemicals/sample was collected and transferred to the electrochemical deposition apparatus containing pure carbon (graphite) electrode, saturated calomel electrode (SCE) and working electrode, Glass substrates. Also, power supply and multimeter which is set to measure voltage and current were connected to the apparatus as shown above in fig 3:1

The molar concentration of selenide source was varied at five different concentration of selenide metal powder, that is, 0.1 M, 0.2 M, 0.4 M and 0.5 M while the molar concentration of AgNO_3 and $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ remain unchanged throughout the experiment. After stirring the mixture of the three samples/reagents collected together, all the three electrodes were immersed into the big container containing the reagents. Wooden guide/non-conductor was used to fasten the electrode erect in place in the container. The DC voltage supply was then switched on at constant voltage of 10 volts and constant time of 5 minutes. The samples B1, B2, B4 and B5 were annealed at 150°C for 5 minutes, while the samples A1, A2, A4, A5 are un-annealed for the same concentrations 0.1 M, 0.2 M, 0.4 M and 0.5 M of selenium source.

Table 3.1: Variation of Molar Concentration of Selenide ion which was annealed at 150°C

S/N	SAMPLE (SP)	CONC. SELENIUM /MOLE (M)	WV / V WORKING VOLTAGE	WC/A WORKING CURRENT
1	B1	0.1	1.00	0.50
2	B2	0.2	1.00	0.50
4	B4	0.4	1.00	0.50
5	B5	0.5	1.00	0.50

Table 3.2: Variation of Molar Concentration of Selenide ion un-annealed.

S/N	SAMPLE (SP)	CONC. SELENIUM /MOLE (M)	WV / V WORKING VOLTAGE	WC/A WORKING CURRENT
1	A1	0.1	1.00	0.50
2	A2	0.2	1.00	0.50
4	A4	0.4	1.00	0.50
5	A5	0.5	1.00	0.50

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

ABSORBANCE.

Figure 4.1: Graph of Absorbance against Wavelength for un-annealed samples (A)

Figure 4.2: Graph of Absorbance against Wavelength for annealed samples (B)

The spectral absorbance of the thin films of Silver Aluminum Selenide (AgAlSe) as a function of wavelength for the un-annealed and annealed samples were displayed in figures 4.1 and 4.2 respectively. The graphs shown that generally the absorbance of the film is high in the UV regions but decreases gradually towards the visible and near infrared regions of the

electromagnetic regions. Besides, the absorbance increases as the molar concentration of the selenide ion increases for the un-annealed sample and decreases for the annealed sample.

4.2: TRANSMITTANCE

Figure 4.3: Graph of % Transmittance against Wavelength for un-annealed samples (A).

Figure 4.4: Graph of % Transmittance against Wavelength for annealed samples (B).

Figures 4.3 and 4.3 are plots of the transmittance against the wavelength of the as deposited thin film samples. The plot indicates that the transmittance of the films is low in the UV region but increases in the VIS and NIR regions. Furthermore, the transmittance of the films increases as the molar concentration of selenide ion increased for the annealed samples but films decreases as the molar concentration of selenide ion increases for the un-annealed sample.

BAND GAP ENERGY.

Figure 4.19: Graph of square of absorption coefficient $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ against Photon Energy $(h\nu)$ for un-annealed samples (A).

The plot of square of absorption coefficient $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ against photon energy $(h\nu)$ for determination of band gap value of the deposited AgAlSe_2 thin films was displayed in figure 4.19 for un-annealed. The band gap of the deposited thin film is in the range of 3.7 to 3.9 eV. The graph also shows that the band gap energy increases with increase in selenide ion concentration for un-annealed samples.

Figure 4.20: Graph of square of absorption coefficient $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ against Photon Energy $(h\nu)$ for annealed samples (B).

Figure 4.20 shows the plot of square of absorption coefficient $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ against photon energy $(h\nu)$ for determination of band gap value of the AgAlSe_2 thin film for the annealed samples. The band gap of the annealed thin film ranges from 3.5 to 3.7 eV as a result of annealing.

COMPOSITIONAL ANALYSIS

Figure 4.25: Compositional analysis of the un-annealed AgAlSe₂ thin film 0.1M (sample A1).

LAYER 1: THICKNESS 1527.10×10^{15} Atoms/cm² or 364 nm

Compo: Ag 70.65% Se 2.60% Al 26.75%

LAYER 4: THICKNESS 14000×10^{15} Atoms/cm² or 3333 nm

Compo:	Si	15.16%	O	55.38%	Ca	1.20%	Na	22.59%
	Al	3.55%	K	0.53%	Fe	0.41%	Mg	
	0.14% Ti	0.95%	S	0.11%				

Figure 4.26: Compositional analysis of the annealed AgAlSe₃ thin film 0.1M (sample B).

LAYER 1: THICKNESS 1657.81×10^{15} Atoms/cm² or 395 nm

Compo: Ag 57.82% Se 12.36% Al 29.82%

LAYER 4: THICKNESS 14000×10^{15} Atoms/cm² or 3333 nm

Compo: Si 15.16% O 55.38% Ca 1.20% Na 22.59%
 Al 3.55% K 0.53% Fe 0.41% Mg
 0.14% Ti 0.95% S 0.11%

The Rutherford Backscattering Spectroscopy (RBS) spectra showing the elements in the grown AgAlSe₂ film were shown in figures 4.25 and 4.26. The composition ratio was found to be 27.2:10.3:1 of atomic mass percent for Ag, Al and Se respectively for the un-annealed film while the composition ratio of 4.6:2.4:1 of atomic mass percent for Ag, Al and Se was obtain for the annealed film. This indicates that the grown films are rich in silver. The silicon, oxygen, calcium, iron, sodium, magnesium, tin, potassium, etc with various percentage detected in layer 4 are believed to have come from the glass substrates used for the deposition.

MICROGRAPHS OF THE DEPOSITED THIN FILMS

Figure 4.27: Micro-graph image of un-annealed AgAlSe₂ (sample A1) 0.1 M.

Figure 4.28: Micro-graph image of un-annealed AgAlSe₂ (sample A2) 0.2 M.

Figure 4.31: Micro-graph image of annealed AgAlSe₂ (sample B1) 0.1 M.

Figure 4.32: Micro-graph image of annealed AgAlSe₂ (sample B2) 0.2 M.

The optical micrograph images of deposited thin films taken to visualize the microstructure of the films are displayed in figures 4.27 to 4.34. The micrograph done at X 10000 magnification with the scale bar length of 100 nm revealed that the deposited films are amorphous in nature, brownish in color, well covered on the glass substrate. The annealing process modifies the morphology of the films. By annealing, the films acquired smooth and crystalline nature.

STRUCTURAL PROPERTIES

Figure 4.21: XRD pattern of sample A1 (0.1M)

Figure 4.22: XRD pattern of sample A2 (0.2M)

Figure 4.23: XRD pattern of sample B1 (0.1M)

Figure 4.24: XRD pattern of sample B2 (0.2M)

The XRD patterns of the deposited thin films of Silver Aluminium Selenide (AgAlSe_2) analyzed using match 3 software for identification are displayed in figure 4.21 to 4.24. The analyses when compared with Crystallography open Database (COD) file number (96-150-9161) shows that the deposited films were Silver Aluminium Selenide (AgAlSe_2). The XRD patterns have preferential orientation at miller indice [112] with 2-theta angle of 26.28° . The

deposited AgAlSe₂ films are of tetragonal crystal structure with lattice constants of $a = 5.956\text{\AA}$, $b = 5.956\text{\AA}$ and $c = 10.750\text{\AA}$. When compared with the reported values of silver selenide thin films by Okereke and Ekpunobi (2011) which reveals the existence of (102), (013), (103), (041) and (232) planes of reflections of orthorhombic phase with lattice constant of $a = 4.33\text{\AA}$, $b = 7.09\text{\AA}$ and $c = 7.76\text{\AA}$ prepared by chemical deposition and Santhosh et al, (2002) who reported the XRD pattern showing (002), (013), (004) and (014) planes of reflections of orthorhombic phase of Ag₂Se prepared by reactive evaporation, one would notice the variation in the structure, the values of the lattice constants which may be as a result of the introduction of the aluminum ion in the present study.

Conclusion

Silver aluminium selenide thin films have been grown by electro-deposition process, which is a low cost, non vacuum and reproductive technique. The effect of annealing on the deposited AgAlSe₂ films was studied. The molar concentration of selenide ion was optimized and found that increasing the selenide ion content increased the crystallinity of the films. The band gap of the deposited thin film are in the range of 3.7 to 3.9 eV but decreases to the range of 3.5 to 3.7eV as a result of annealing and generally as the molar concentration of selenide source increases the band gap energy of the deposited samples decreases. The results of the X-ray diffraction (XRD) showed that the deposited AgAlSe₂ films are of tetragonal crystal structure. Also, the results of the RBS analysis showed that the grown films are rich in silver. Therefore, the obtained results on AgAlSe₂ p-type semiconductor thin films make them desirable for photovoltaic devices, optical and opto-electronic application. Since, such semiconductor materials allow power electronic components to be smaller, faster, more reliable and more efficient.

5. REFERENCES

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